

Synthesis and Characterisation of Nickel(II) Complexes : Ligand Field Parameters and Nephelauxetic Effect

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In continuation of our studies¹, we report herein synthesis and characterisation of nickel(II) complexes of new Schiff bases derived from 4-(*p*-R.C₆H₄)-2-aminothiazole (R = H, CH₃, OCH₃, Cl, OC₂H₅) and 4-methylsalicylaldehyde. The Schiff bases were prepared by condensation of 4-methylsalicylaldehyde and 4-(*p*-R.C₆H₄)-2-aminothiazole. Nickel(II) complexes were prepared by reacting Schiff base with nickel acetate.

Results and Discussion

All the Schiff bases (Table 1) are crystalline

yellow solids having sharp m.p. and are soluble in common organic solvents. The electronic spectrum of 2-aminothiazole exhibits band at ~ 275 nm while other aromatic amino compounds with comparable structures absorb at ~ 300 nm². The shifting of the ligand band (~ 400 nm) towards longer wavelength may be due to extended conjugation³ in the molecule. The IR spectra of the ligands show a weak and broad bands at ~ 2 900 (phenolic OH), $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{C-O} modes ~ 1 630 (C=N) and ~ 1 280 cm⁻¹ (C-O), the latter two are in agreement with the reported data⁴.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS DATA OF THE LIGANDS AND THE COMPLEXES

R of Schiff base	Mol formula	Analysis% Found/(Calcd)			Mol wt Found/ (Calcd)
		N	S	Ni	
H	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ OS	9.42 (9.50)	10.50 (10.88)		253 (294)
	Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ OS) ₂ (1)	8.80 (8.68)	9.70 (9.92)	8.95 (9.13)	602 (645)
CH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ OS	8.80 (9.09)	10.10 (10.38)	279	(308)
	Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O S) ₂ (2)	8.05 (8.32)	9.50 (9.31)	8.53 (8.75)	622 (673)
OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.40 (8.64)	9.70 (9.87)		296 (324)
	Ni(C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (3)	7.70 (7.94)	9.00 (9.07)	8.20 (8.36)	653 (705)
Cl	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl N ₂ O S	8.40 (8.52)	9.50 (9.74)	310	(329)
	Ni(C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Cl N ₂ O S) ₂ (4)	7.93 (7.84)	8.80 (8.96)	8.38 (8.26)	668 (714)
OC ₂ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.09 (8.28)	9.29 (9.46)		300 (338)
	Ni(C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S) ₂ (5)	7.48 (7.64)	8.80 (8.74)	7.90 (8.00)	700 (733)

The complexes (Table 1) are greenish yellow crystalline solids and melt with decomposition above 250°. They are soluble in chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene. The complexes possess 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry, having monomeric and non-electrolytic nature.

Electronic spectra : Electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit three bands at 8 000, 13 500 and 24 000 cm^{-1} assigned to transitions ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, $(\nu_1) {}^3T_{1g}(F) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ and $(\nu_2) {}^3T_{1g}(P) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_3), and the fourth band at $\sim 26\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon = 1000\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to $L \rightarrow M$ charge transfer. The electronic spectral data suggest an octahedral geometry⁵ for the complexes.

The ligand field parameters data are given in Table 2. The values of B (800–900 cm^{-1}) are less than the free metal ion (1 041 cm^{-1})⁶ value. The value of β (~ 0.9) indicates considerable covalent character in metal ligand bond⁷.

The values of Racah parameters⁸ B , C , nephelauxetic ratio⁹ β , Slater Condon parameters (F_2 and F_4), Slater Condon shorted parameters (F^2 and F^4) of the complexes¹⁰, ν_3/ν_1 (2.97), ν_3/ν_2 (1.8) and Dq/B (0.90–0.92) support an octahedral geometry for the complexes. The nephelauxetic parameter¹¹ (h_x) values (1.21–1.36) suggest that the ligands should be placed between urea and ammonia in the nephelauxetic series¹².

Infrared spectra : Absence of ν_{OH} mode in the complexes (which occurs at $\sim 2\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands) indicates the involvement of OH group in M–O bond formation. The complexes reveal $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ mode at $\sim 1\,330$ (at $\sim 1\,280\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands) and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ mode at $\sim 1\,580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (at $\sim 1\,630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands). The shifting of $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ towards higher frequency in the complexes as compared to the ligands, is due to conversion of hydrogen-bonded

structure to a covalent metal bonded structure⁴. The shifting of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ mode towards lower frequency in the complexes as compared to the ligands, suggests coordination through nitrogen of the azomethine group⁴. The occurrence of a broad and weak non-ligand band at $\sim 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes may be due to $\nu_{\text{Ni-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Ni-O}}$ modes¹³. Thus infrared spectral data suggest coordination to the central metal atom through nitrogen of the azomethine group and oxygen of the phenolic OH group.

Mass spectra : Mass spectra of Schiff base metal complexes were studied to determine molecular weights¹⁴. Some nickel Schiff base complexes give abnormal mass spectra due to formation of binuclear species¹⁵. No peaks with m/z ratio higher than that of molecular ion (M^+) (m/z 645) were observed in the present case. This excludes the formation of polymeric species.

Magnetic susceptibility : The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes (Gouy method) lie in the range 3.0–3.2 B.M. suggesting an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹⁶.

Experimental

Physical measurements were carried out as described earlier¹. The molecular weights of the ligands and the complexes were determined by cryoscopic method using benzene as the solvent. Mass spectra of the complexes were run on a Hitachi Perkin-Elmer spectrometer (70 eV) and at an inlet temperature of 300° at the Department of Chemistry, Moscow State University, Moscow.

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TABLE-2 LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd no	$10Dq$	B	C	b	F_2	F_4	F^2	F^4
1	8 000	873	4 110	0 836	1 460	1 17 4	71 540	51 773
2	8 000	886	4 172	0 851	1 482	119 2	72 618	52 567
3	8 000	890	4 191	0 854	1 488	119 7	72 912	52 787
4	8 050	876	4 125	0 841	1 466	118 0	71 834	51 993
5	8 100	880	4 143	0 845	1 473	118 3	72 079	52 170

*Corresponds to that in Table 1

NOTE

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